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ABSTRACT

Forecasting stock prices is a crucial aspect of informed financial decision-making and strategic investment planning. This research endeavors to elevate the precision of stock price predictions and decision-making by leveraging multilayered Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) networks with Dynamic Indicator (DI) features, as proposed by J. Huang *et al.* [2]. The study conducts a comparative analysis between the predictive performance of conventional LSTM models and the innovative incremental BiLSTM models as discussed by D.Rajesh *et al.* [6]. These models incorporate a comprehensive set of both fundamental and technical analysis parameters, aiming to enhance overall accuracy and provide robust decision support. The research conducted by Zhang R *et al.* [5] has predominantly centered on the utilization of fundamental parameters and technical parameters are highlighted by D.Rajesh *et al.* [3]. Additionally, we incorporated key indicators such as Relative Strength Index (RSI), Stochastic Oscillator, Price Rate of Change (ROC), and Average True Range (ATR), as these features have demonstrated potential in the accurate prediction of stock prices when employing LSTM models Binod Rimal *et al.* [8]. Despite the promising results, the inherent limitations of LSTM models in capturing intricate temporal dependencies have prompted the exploration of more advanced architectural frameworks. This paper introduces a novel methodology for developing Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) model with DIF, as demonstrated for enhanced performance by Rishabh *et al.* [7], leveraging carefully chosen input variables. The performance of the proposed approach is assessed based on metrics such as Directional Accuracy, Hit Rate, and Quantile Loss. Experimental results reveal that the BiLSTM with DIF model outperforms the incremental BiLSTM model D.Rajesh *et al.* [6], demonstrating a superior fit to the data and achieving higher prediction accuracy.

Keywords: Stock price prediction, Multilayered Bidirectional LSTM, DIF, RSI, ROC, and ATR.

1. INTRODUCTION

Precisely predicting stock prices has posed a persistent challenge in the finance and investment. Researchers have continuously investigated diverse methodologies to improve prediction accuracy, incorporating insights from both fundamental, as highlighted by Varun Rastogi *et al.* [9], and technical indicators. In contemporary research, deep learning approaches, notably Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models, have demonstrated significant promise in effectively capturing intricate patterns and relationships within financial time series data, as observed in the work of Pushparaj *et al.* [10].

This work endeavors to extend the advancements made in predicting stock prices through LSTM models by enhancing complexity and context. Building upon the work of J. Huang *et al.* [2], Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) models will be employed. This approach integrates fundamental parameters (such as open, close, high, low, and volume) and technical parameters (including Moving Average, Exponential Moving Average (EMA), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), Bollinger Bands, and Momentum. Additionally, we incorporated key indicators such as Relative Strength Index (RSI), Stochastic Oscillator, Price Rate of

Change (ROC), and Average True Range (ATR) as suggested by *Binod Rimal et al. [8]*. The goal is to provide a more comprehensive methodology for capturing the intricate dynamics of stock price movements.

This study introduces an innovative methodology utilizing Multilayered Bidirectional LSTM networks with DIF to augment prediction accuracy. Leveraging the Multilayered nature of the model allows for the incorporation of both past and future data points, effectively capturing temporal dependencies that influence stock price behavior. The research goes beyond simple price forecasting by extending predictive capabilities to include the estimation of stock volatility and the generation of buy and sell decision signals.

The following segments in this paper present a review of related works, an in-depth exploration of the methodology employed, details of the experimental setup, the outcomes and their analysis, and a final section comprising conclusions and avenues for future research. This study endeavors to deliver an all-encompassing and resilient solution for predicting stock prices by incorporating diverse aspects of financial data analysis. The overarching goal is to empower investors with insightful information, facilitating well-informed and strategic investment decisions.

2. RELATED WORK

The stock market is a captivating industry with numerous intricacies. Experts have dedicated considerable efforts to studying and analyzing the various trends within the stock market. A significant focus of this research has been on predicting stock prices based on historical data *Srinath Ravikumar et al. [1]*. Accurate predictions can provide valuable insights for investors, guiding them on where and how to invest to minimize the risk of financial loss. This predictive application holds potential utility for companies engaging in Initial Public Offerings (IPOs), helping them determine target values and the optimal number of shares to release. The field has witnessed substantial advancements, with many researchers exploring machine learning and deep learning as promising avenues for stock price prediction. The proposed system operates through two methods – Regression, predicting the closing price of a company's stock, and Classification, predicting whether the closing price will increase or decrease the following day.

Forecasting stock index prices is a common pursuit in both academic and economic spheres, presenting challenges due to inherent uncertainties and noise. With the advancements in computer science, neural networks have found applications across various industries. *Zhang R et al. [5]* explores four distinct machine learning methods, encompassing three conventional models: Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and an attention-based neural network. The primary objective is to predict the next day's index price based on historical data. The dataset incorporates the SP500 index, CSI300 index, and Nikkei225 index from three diverse financial markets, representing highly developed, less developed, and developing markets, respectively. Seven variables, including daily trading data, technical indicators, and macroeconomic variables, are selected as inputs. Results indicate that the attention-based model outperforms the other models, and notably, all introduced models exhibit higher accuracy in developed financial markets compared to developing ones.

The rapid progress in artificial intelligence and machine learning, coupled with the availability of extensive datasets and enhanced computational capabilities, has paved the way for the development of sophisticated methods in stock price prediction. Simultaneously, the ease of access to investment opportunities has heightened the complexity and volatility of the stock market. There is a growing demand for an accurate and reliable predictive model capable of comprehensively capturing the market's highly volatile and nonlinear behavior. *Binod Rimal et al. [8]* employs a long short-term memory (LSTM), a specific neural network architecture, to forecast the next-day closing price of the S&P 500 index. A well-balanced combination of nine predictors is thoughtfully crafted, encompassing fundamental market data, macroeconomic data, and technical indicators to capture the broader behavior of the stock market. Single-layer and multilayer LSTM models are constructed using the chosen input variables, and their performances are assessed using standard metrics, including Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), and Correlation Coefficient (R). The experimental results indicate that the single-layer LSTM model offers a superior fit and high prediction accuracy compared to multilayer LSTM models.

Rajesh et al [6] outlines the development and application of a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model for stock price prediction based on technical analysis. The model incorporates various technical indicators, such as moving averages and Bollinger Bands, to identify trends in the stock market and predict future stock values. Historical stock data is utilized to derive these technical indicators, which, in turn, serve as input features for training the LSTM model through a supervised learning approach. Performance evaluation metrics, including mean absolute error, mean squared error, and root mean squared error, are employed to assess the model's effectiveness. However, with the increased accessibility of investment opportunities, the stock market has become more intricate and volatile. To address this, the paper introduces a stock price prediction system utilizing an LSTM-oriented neural network to forecast the next-day closing price of APPLE shares. Regression and LSTM models are developed using selected input variables, and their performance is analyzed using RMSE, MAPE, and R-squared error metrics to discern the stock's trend for buying and selling decisions.

Significantly influencing financial decision-making and investment strategies, stock price prediction is a critical aspect of market analysis. *Rajesh et al [3]* focuses on advancing stock price prediction accuracy and decision-making precision by leveraging Incremental Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) networks, a comparative analysis is conducted between the predictive capabilities of traditional LSTM models, and the proposed Incremental BiLSTM model. The comparison incorporates both fundamental and technical analysis parameters have predominantly concentrated on utilizing fundamental parameters such as open, close, high, low, and volume, coupled with technical parameters like Moving Average, Exponential Moving Average (EMA), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), Bollinger Bands, and Momentum, These features exhibit promise in stock price prediction using LSTM models. However, the limitations of LSTM models in capturing intricate temporal dependencies have prompted exploration into more advanced architectures. In this paper, we introduce a novel approach, implementing Incremental Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) models for enhanced performance, the method's effectiveness is evaluated based on Directional Accuracy, Hit Rate, and Quantile Loss. Experimental findings suggest that the incremental BiLSTM model demonstrates a superior fit to the data compared to the single-layer BiLSTM model, achieving higher prediction accuracy.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data Collection and Preprocessing:

The data for APPLE stock was acquired from Yahoo Finance in a .csv format and stored in an MS Excel document, encompassing a total of 5283 days of data. This dataset includes fundamental information such as open, high, low, and close prices, along with technical indicators like Moving Average, Exponential Moving Averages (EMA), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), Bollinger Bands, and Momentum. Additionally, we incorporated key indicators such as Relative Strength Index (RSI), Stochastic Oscillator, Price Rate of Change (ROC), and Average True Range (ATR) as technical indicators involve mathematical calculations applied to data, including price or other technical aspects, commonly utilized by active traders for analyzing short-term price movements. The dataset spans from January 2001 to December 2020. To ensure consistent data quality, perform data preprocessing tasks such as missing value imputation, normalization, and feature scaling.

S. No.	Feature	Description
1	Open Price	Opening price of the stock on a particular day
2	Close Price	The closing price of the stock at the end of a trading day
3	High Price	The peak price on a particular day
4	Low Price	The lowest price of the stock on a particular day
5	Volume	Represents the total number of shares traded in a given period
6	Moving Average (MA)	Smooth's out price data over a specified time period
7	Exponential Moving Average (EMA)	Smooth's out price data as it assigns more weight to recent prices.
8	Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD)	Calculates the difference between short-term and long-term moving averages
9	Bollinger Bands	Price's standard deviation from the middle line
10	Momentum	Rate of change in price over a specific time period

11	Relative Strength Index (RSI)	A momentum oscillator that measures the speed and change of price movements. It ranges from 0 to 100.
12	Stochastic Oscillator	A momentum indicator that compares the closing price of a security to a range of its prices over a certain period
13	Price Rate of Change (ROC)	Measures the percentage change in price between the most recent closing price and the closing price N periods ago.
14	Average True Range (ATR)	Measures market volatility by calculating the moving average of a stock's true range over a specified time period.

Table 1: List of potential features for the model

3.2 Algorithm for BiLSTM DIF Model

1. Input preparation:

Load dataset and include new features (RSI, Stochastic Oscillator, Price Rate of Change, Average and Average True Range).

Select existing fundamental and technical features.

Preprocess data, including scaling.

Define features (X) and target variable (y).

2. Split datasets:

Split data into training and testing sets.

3. Model Initialization:

Initialize number of epochs (epochs).

Set up model architecture:

Create a BiLSTM model with specified architecture.

Compile the model with chosen hyperparameters (optimizer, learning rate).

4. Data Reshaping:

Reshape data for LSTM input (samples, time steps, features).

Create sequences for training and testing datasets.

5. Training Loop:

FOR each epoch FROM 1 to epochs DO

Train the model on the training data with the chosen batch size.

Use validation data for monitoring and early stopping.

IF early stopping criteria met THEN

END DO (Stop training)

END IF

CONTINUE

END FOR

6. Model Evaluation:

Evaluate the trained model on the test data.

Obtain performance metrics (e.g., loss).

7. Output:

Return the final trained BiLSTM model.

END

4. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The implementation of the proposed models occurred on a Windows 10 system featuring an Intel i3 processor, 8 GB of RAM, and an NVidia GeForce GTX 512 graphics processor.

4.1 Preprocessing the Dataset

The collected dataset comprises OHLC (Open, High, Low, Close, and Volume) prices, containing a total of 5283 samples. This dataset was divided into training and testing sets using an 80:20 ratio. After removing any null values, the data underwent a cleaning process. Subsequently, the MinMaxScaler from the sklearn library was utilized to normalize the data. This normalization method involves subtracting the minimum value in the dataset from each data point and then dividing every data point by the maximum value in the dataset. This procedure was applied to multiple time series, each representing Opening Price, Closing Price, High Price, and Low Price and Volume.

4.2. Input Layer

The input matrix is composed of ten distinct columns: Open, High, Low, Close, Volume, and a set of technical indicators including Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), Moving Average (MA), Exponential Moving Average (EMA), Bollinger Bands, and Momentum Relative Strength Index (RSI), Stochastic Oscillator, Price Rate of Change (ROC), and Average True Range (ATR). These columns collectively constitute a time series dataset.

The output matrix consists of a solitary column named "Adjusted Close," which determines the market's opening price for the subsequent day.

The data was divided into a training set and a test set with a ratio of 13:1.

Following the normalization process, every element of the input data has been transformed to fall within the range of 0 to 1.

Each entry within our dataset incorporates the preceding one hundred days as its input, resulting in our input dataset being structured as a 3-D matrix with dimensions (N, 100, 13).

4.3. Implementation of BI-LSTM model using DIF features

The central purpose of the Multilayered Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) with DIF is to discern the information that should be retained or discarded within the Bi-LSTM cell, as illustrated in *Rajesh et al [3]*. This determination is facilitated by the sigmoid layer. When the output is '0', the information is disregarded, while an output of '1' signifies information retention.

Fig 2: Multilayered BiLSTM with DIF.

The subsequent stage involves determining the specific information to be stored within the Bi-LSTM cell. This task is carried out through a set of multi layers incorporated within the Bi-LSTM cell. The initial layer features a sigmoid activation, responsible for discerning the values to be updated in order to attain the intended output. The subsequent layer is implemented using the tanh activation function. This layer assumes the responsibility of generating fresh candidate values, which can be utilized within our Bi-LSTM cell at a later point. Following

this, the two layers are merged to formulate a novel Bi-LSTM cell state, housing solely the essential information.

The outcome of the Bi-LSTM yields a refined iteration of our cell state. We subject this output to a tanh function to constrain its value range between -1 and 1. Following this transformation, we merge the output with the sigmoid layer, ensuring that the throughput is tailored to meet our specific criteria. As a result, only the pertinent information is presented as the final output.

Fig 3: The proposed model architecture for stock price prediction.

4.4. Hyperparameter Tuning

The process of selecting the optimal model architecture involves thorough exploration across two main categories: (a) Incremental BiLSTM and (b) BiLSTM DIF. In the Incremental BiLSTM model, there exists two LSTM layers within the model. Conversely, in the BiLSTM DIF model, there are multiple LSTM layers integrated into the model. In the context of the Incremental BiLSTM architecture is experimented employing with (10,5), (20,10), (50,20), (100,50), and (100,50,20) six distinct neurons, all optimized using the Adam optimizer learning rate 0.001 and batch size is 64. Each model undergoes 10 executions for every combination of hyperparameters, and the RMSE score is computed. The selection of the most optimal hyperparameter combination for a given model based on achieving the lowest RMSE score when evaluated on the validation data. Likewise, the most suitable hyperparameters are determined for six distinct BiLSTM DIF models, characterized by configurations such as (20, 10, 5), (50, 20, 10), (100, 50, 20), (150, 100, 50), (200, 150, 100) and (450, 400, 350) neurons. In this context, the notation (n1, n2, n3) represents the configuration of the first, second and third hidden layers.

4.5 Model Performance Metrics

4.5.1 Direction accuracy - Evaluates the directional correctness of a predictive model it measures the percentage of correct directional predictions made by the model, it assesses whether the model correctly predicts whether the target variable will go up or down. Direction accuracy is typically used when the goal is not only to predict the exact value of a target variable but also to capture the overall trend or direction of the variable.

$$\text{Direction Accuracy} = (\text{Number of Correct Directional Predictions}) / (\text{Total Number of Predictions}) * 100$$

Where:

"Number of Correct Directional Predictions" is the count of predictions where the model correctly predicted the direction (e.g., the model predicted an increase, and the actual value increased).

"Total Number of Predictions" is the total number of predictions made by the model.

4.5.2 Hit rate - It is also known as the true positive rate (TPR) or sensitivity, is a performance metric used in binary classification to measure the proportion of true positive predictions (correctly predicted positives) out of all actual positive instances. It quantifies the model's ability to correctly identify positive cases.

$TPR = \text{True Positives (TP)} / \text{True Positives (TP)} + \text{False Negatives (FN)}$

True Positives (TP) are the instances that are actually positive and correctly predicted as positive by the model.

False Negatives (FN) are the instances that are actually positive but incorrectly predicted as negative by the model.

4.5.3 Quantile loss - To evaluate the accuracy of predicted quantiles or percentiles of the target variable. It measures the discrepancy between the predicted quantiles and the actual quantiles of the target variable.

$$\ell(y, \hat{y}) = \begin{cases} \alpha \cdot (y - \hat{y}) & , \hat{y} \leq y \\ (1 - \alpha) \cdot (\hat{y} - y) & , \hat{y} > y \end{cases}$$

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 BiLSTM DIF Results

BiLSTM DIF model is trained using the training dataset, and the selection of the optimal model is based on performance scores computed using the test dataset. The data entries displayed in Table 2 represent the performance scores between Incremental BiLSTM vs BiLSTM DIF model illustrates that the model featuring (450, 400, 350) neurons outperforms Incremental BiLSTM. Furthermore, it highlights that BiLSTM DIF models exhibit improved performance compared to Incremental BiLSTM.

	BiLSTM DIF	Incremental BiLSTM	LSTM TA	LSTM FA
Directional Accuracy	0.71	0.63	0.50	0.48
Hit Rate	0.82	0.74	0.63	0.61
Quantile Loss	0.74	1.00	1.67	1.91

Table 2: Comparison of performance scores of different models.

Fig 4(a) The resulting plot provides a visual comparison of the actual Apple stock prices and the predictions made by four models along with performance (percentage deviation) relative to the actual prices. This allows for an easy visual assessment of how well each model performs in predicting stock prices. **Fig 4(b)** The resulting plot shows the directional accuracy scores for each of the four models over the sequence of predictions. It allows for a visual comparison of how well each model performs in terms of directional accuracy as the sequence progresses.

4(a)

4(b)

Fig 4(c) The scatter plot represent the predicted values compared to the actual values, and the diagonal red dashed line represents perfect predictions. Points close to this line, indicating accurate predictions, points above the line indicate over predictions, and points below the line indicate under predictions. Fig 4(d) The resulting bar graph visually represents quantile loss values for each quantile level and time step. This visualization helps in understanding how different quantile levels and time steps impact the performance of the models, particularly in terms of predicting extreme quantiles.

Fig 4(e) & 4(f) represents the scatter plot to measure the performance obtained from different models using RMSE and MAE metrics.

4(e)

4(f)

Fig 4(g) the residual plot helps visualize the relationship between predicted values and their corresponding residuals for each model. R^2 values provide a measure of how well each model fits the data, and the horizontal line at $y = 0$ helps identify patterns of overestimation or underestimation in the predictions.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The proposed BiLSTM DIF model introduced in this paper has demonstrated superior performance compared to standard models. Its potential is especially promising when contrasted with previous methodologies. BiLSTM DIF model has captured **DA** of **0.71** which indicate us how well the model performs in terms of directional accuracy as the sequence progresses which is better result when compared to the Incremental BiLSTM model value is **0.63**. In terms of **quantile loss** also BiLSTM DIF has shown loss of **0.74** when compared with Incremental BiLSTM **0.81**. Leveraging extensive datasets has allowed our model to uncover more intricate patterns, enabling better calibration of layer weights. Multilayered Bi-directional LSTM with DIF prove advantageous by retaining information from both past and future states, facilitating tracking of short-term dependencies within stock prices over extended periods.

Comparing our model to other stock prediction methods reveals a noteworthy improvement in accuracy. In the coming times, our research aims to delve into the integration of unstructured textual data into our predictive models. This includes incorporating data like investor sentiment gathered from social media, earnings reports from underlying companies, immediate policy-related news, and research reports provided by market analysts. Additionally, we are considering the exploration of hybrid predictive models that combine LSTM with other neural network architectures. Our future endeavors involve the implementation of hybrid optimization algorithms. These algorithms will combine existing local optimizers with global optimizers such as genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimization algorithms to fine-tune model parameters effectively.

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